

Understanding growth mechanism through agriculture and agro-industry investment: A micro-funded DSGE model applied to Benin

Selidji Caroline Tossou*

Abstract

Benin GDP growth was respectively 2.1%, 4.0%, 5.6% and 6% from 2015 to 2018 (World Bank 2018). Despite this positive performance of the economy over the last decade, population below poverty line was 36.2% and GINI index of Benin increased from 38.6 in 2003 to 47.8 in 2015, growing at an average annual rate of 11.29%. This unequal distribution of the wealth can be resolved through a system of integrated growth, by fully exploiting high potential sectors such as agriculture and agro-industry in order to avoid a deterioration of the situation of the vulnerable households. This paper examines the impact of alternative growth paths through investments in agriculture and agro-industry sectors combined. We use a micro funded DSGE Model associated with the Social Accounting Matrix (SAM) of Benin of the year 2013 where we simulate an increase of 75% of capital in the agriculture and agro-industry sectors from 2017 to 2022. The results of the model indicate an increase of the GDP by almost 6% per year during the period of investment that will continue to increase after 2021. In addition, this induce more production in agriculture (average yearly growth of 6 %) and agro industry sectors (average yearly growth of 11%) and also other sectors as financial services, transport and trade and ameliorate the wellbeing of the society as a whole.

Key words: Development and growth, Dynamic Stochastic General Equilibrium model; Social Accounting Matrix, Government Action Plan, Policy Simulations.

*Assistant Professor, San Juan College

Introduction

It is almost an orthodox belief in the literature that agriculture and agro-industry generate growth and thus are great tools to fueling economic development. The objective of this paper is to evaluate this role of increasing capital investment in both agriculture and agro-industry sectors in Benin.

In a low-income country like Benin, agriculture is not only necessary for economic growth and poverty alleviation, but also counts for food security achievement and is the ground for raw materials essential for industrialization especially agrobusiness. For example, Pinstруп-Anderson and Satoru Shimokawa 2007 have shown in their paper titled Rural Infrastructure and Agricultural Development that Agriculture is the backbone for the less-developed countries to take off.

The relevance of this study is to understand the regional development in relation to agro based industries. The prospects of this industry is undoubtedly bright because majority of farmers in Benin region depends on agricultural activities so there is a need to develop agro-industry activities so that people get jobs in their villages to improve their standard of living. In addition, agro-industries play a vital role by generating substantial employment, earnings and foreign exchange for the country. It has also the capacity to transform any harvest losses in the agricultural sector. Besides the opportunities of domestic market and in the area of export it can contribute to open up rural society with the development of dynamic economic institutions and Benins industrial policy. Industries will motivate farmers for better production, which will help to develop leadership, entrepreneurship and formation of cooperatives to work together in rural society. This study can also be useful for the Government for micro and macro level regional planning for developing economic activities. The study is also useful for agricultural entrepreneur, exporters, for their future plan.

There is therefore a need to build an adequate strategy that puts Benin progressively and permanently safe from food insecurity and that inscribes it in a sustainable approach to creating wealth. All policy in the Development Plan Documents in Benin, sectoral or global, give priority to the agriculture and agro industry sectors in order to raise the standard of living of the Beninese.

As instrument of this analysis, we use a Dynamic and Stochastic General Equilibrium Model to analyze the impact of a 75 % increase of the existed capital in the two sectors. According to Ian Sue Wing (2004), this model is the one that fit the most with the objective of this paper.

DSGE models are widely used in policy analysis, especially in developing-country academic setting. It uses actual economic data to describe the behavior of all economic agents and to estimate the reaction of an economy according to some changes.

Those changes can be in policy, technology or some external factors and its explicitly represent the potential transmission channels of the simulated shocks. For Alpana et al (2011), DSGE models are used to simulate the interrelationships between different factors and markets following a structural change in the economy. Despite the data limitations faced by most developing countries, these models make it possible to evaluate in a precise way the global impact of economic policies, but also and above all to identify micro and meso-economic channels of transmission of the effects of these countries' policies on their economies. So DSGE models are a tool that is used to simulate economic policies and structural shocks in order to help governments or international organizations in their decision-making.

These models have been used in different areas like fiscal reform and development planning (e.g., Perry et al 2001; Gunning and Keyzer 1995), international trade (e.g., Shields and Francois 1994; Martin and Winters 1996; Harrison et al 1997), and increasingly, environmental regulation (e.g., Weyant 1999; Bovenberg and Goulder 1996; Goulder 2002).

However, despite the many uses of DSGE, these models are not suitable for evaluating policies at the level of an individual or a company, for example. General equilibrium analyzes are carried out at the cost of several assumptions of homogeneity and rationality of economic agents. For example, the use of representative households could only partially capture the heterogeneity of households. However, these models are still the best tool for assessing macro, meso and sectoral effects of public policies and / or international shocks.

DSGE analysis, may present two limits. The first is that DSGE analysis require huge data and a lot of time to collect updated, high-quality, to build the Social Accounting Matrices, and program and calibrate a DSGE model. A second attention should be made about how we interpret the results that should base on directions and distributive patterns rather than numeric outcomes themselves.

To be able to use the DSGE Model, we associate it to the Social Accounting Matrix (SAM) for Benin accounts and the General Algebraic Modeling System (GAMS). The Social Accounting Matrix that describe the whole interaction pattern between all agents and the different economic sectors is constructed by Benin National Statistic Institute for Economic Analyses (INSAE). Once the model constructed, we simulate the different policies and analyze their impacts.

Our findings mainly exposed the benefits of the investment in capital in those main sectors on the country. We find out a positive and sustained growth of the GDP throughout many years. Further, apart from the direct positive impact on the main sectors, this induces more production in other sectors as economic services, trade and transport and also generate revenues for households, government and enterprises.

1 Benin Historical context

The Beninese economy has evolved into two systems, including the planned economy system and the market economy system. The planned economy, which lasted from 1972 to 1989, was marked by the centralization of the role of the State in economic activities, resulting in poor allocation of resources, excessive public sector development, private sector atrophy and an imbalance in the operating budget. Thus from 1990, years of the advent of democracy, the country opted for economic liberalism. Since then, Benin has been engaged in a process of economic and financial reform, supported by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and the World Bank (WB). Significant reforms have been undertaken in several areas. Changes in the country's management system and economic reforms in the early 1990s have contributed to the gradual restoration of macroeconomic balances and the strengthening of economic growth. These reforms made it possible to improve the macroeconomic framework, consolidate public finances and achieve an average annual growth rate of 5% between 1996 and 2001. The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Benin expanded 5% in the third quarter of 2016 over the same quarter of the previous year. GDP annual growth rate in Benin averaged 3.83% from 1961 until 2016, reaching an all time high level of 9.95% in the fourth quarter of 1981 and a low record of -4.90% in the fourth quarter of 1975 (Institut National de la Statistique et de l'Analyse Economique INSAE (2017)). From the same source, we can see that from the three previous years up to now, Benin GDP growth rate has fluctuated a lot. This is represented in the figure 1.

Figure 1: Benin GDP annual growth rate from 2014 to 2016

Source : INSAE (2017)

Given the situation of the economy that seem to be more stable than many other countries in the figure 2, we may expect positive effects but the real change expected is still not achieved because we are witnessing a deterioration of the living conditions of the population until today.

To face the different problems and stabilize Benin economy, the new President Talon has elaborate a clear, precise and detailed Government Action Plan (GAP) and disseminated to all actors and at all levels of civil society. The GAP is structured

Figure 2: Comparison between Benin and its borderer countries

Source : World Bank (2017)

around 45 sectoral projects and 95 prioritized project aimed at improving the productivity and living conditions of the Beninese population. It clearly identifies the financial and human resources that will be allocated and/or adjusted to the different implementation periods and the different sectors of the Beninese economy that will be affected. President Talon has also pursued one of the main subjects of his presidential campaign to reform the Beninese political model.

Compared with the more aggregated structuring of the Structural Adjustment and Poverty Reduction policies which had been strongly recommended to the precedent government by the Breton Wood institutions, this detailed and pointed structuring of the GAP should prove to be a decisive advantage for the achievement of the development objectives, especially that of being able to predict the future impacts of the GAP and, able to anticipate adjustments that might be necessary.

2 Methodology

2.1 Data and Social Accounting Matrix (SAM)

The data used in the study is the Social Accounting Matrix (SAM) 2013 of Benin. The SAM is constructed by the National Institute of Statistic and Economic Analyses of Benin (INSAE) using various data sources like the Economic Table that is an Integrated Economic Accounts Table and the Resources-Employment Table (TRE) that is an In-Out Table for Benin. The SAM is a table and a square matrix that summarizes the statistical data of the various sectors and agents of the economy so that the total revenues is equal to the total expenditure. All real flows of the economy are represented in the accounting matrix, so that one can easily describe the interrelationships that exist between the various agents and sectors of the economy. According to the assumptions of our model, the social accounting matrix of Benin for the year 2013 shows that the economy of Benin, into this date, integrates 4 economic

Figure 3: Distribution of the capital in 2013

Source : SAM (2013)

Figure 4: Distribution of the labor in 2013

Source : SAM (2013)

agents (Households, Firms, Government and Rest Of World), 2 factors of production (Labor and Capital) , 21 branches of activity, 21 compound products, 17 product of importation and 16 products of exportation.

SAM-2013 breaks up the sources of income of the households into four components which are; wages, dividends of the return on capital, the transfer from the government (social assistances) and the transfer of funds coming from the rest of the world. In 2013, the commercial balance of Benin economy was a deficit. For our study, we used all the 21 branches of activity available in the Resource-employment table to represent the most completely possible the economy of Benin. It is composed of 17 sectors capable to produce goods and 4 capable to produce service.

The distribution of the factors of production (capital and labour) of these branches

is detailed in the following figure 3 and 4. Capital and labor are the two factors used in the production process in the 21 branches of activity to produce their output.

According to the figures, the branch Agriculture used more capital. This sector is seen like pillar of the economy of Benin. Agriculture alone used until 20% of the total capital followed by the commerce sector (13%) and transport and telecommunication (12%). The workforce, however, remains present in the production process in Benin, although its share has drastically decreased. The three main sectors that use it more intensively are the services sectors of public administration, education and the transport sector. Together they employ more than 60% of the available labor force in 2013. It should be emphasized that the Beninese economy in terms of labor is strongly dominated by the informal sector. According to the Integrated Modular Survey on Living Conditions (EMICOV) carried out in 2010 by INSAE, the informal sector employs more than 95% of the total workforce. This mean that the Beninese economy effectively exploits only 5% of its available workforce.

According to Ricardo's theory of comparative advantages, each country should specialize, thus investing more in sectors for which it has a comparative advantage in international trade, in other words the sectors in which it is most productive. The study of the productivity of the factors involved in the production process of the different sectors of the Beninese economy will make it possible to identify the potential productivity gains which the national economy could benefit from the different sectors of which it is composed while comparing these data history of the PAG. The graphs 5 below give a brief indication of the productivity levels of capital and labor factors combined in each sector of the national economy.

Graph 5 shows that the most productive sectors of the national economy are the petroleum refinery, the glass-making industry, and the other agro-food industries. The sectors of production of public administration services, electricity, gas and water, education and textile manufacturing are the least productive in 2013.

2.2 Description of the model

The model that we built belong to the framework of the neo-keynesian theory of general equilibrium. The model takes as a starting point the static model EXTER drawn from Decaluwé et al. (2001), that was built to represent a small open economy world price taker. In our case, we will build a dynamic model to overpass the limits of the static model and even make it stochastic. Our model is then a Dynamic and Stochastic General Equilibrium model DSGE. It comprises in total 10,551 endogenous equations and 10,551 variables over 10 periods. These equations describe the behavior of 4 economic agents (households, the Government, firms and the rest of the world),

Figure 5: Productivity of the sectors in 2013

Source : SAM (2013)

the behavior of the 21 branches of activity of the economy and the equations of price and balances in the budget.

2.3 The calibration of the model

The calibration can be defined as the determination of the parameters and the coefficients so as to reconstitute a situation of equilibrium of the reference period. It represents the choice of the numerical values of the parameters of the functional forms retained in the DSGE. Like the majority of the DSGE, ours was calibrated primarily from SAM-2013. Thus by deduction, using the reversed equations of the model, we could obtain the major part of our parameters in order to find a situation of equilibrium. Only the free parameters which are elasticities of substitution and transformation were deduced differently by taking into account specificities from each branch of activity and by referring to the existing literature.

2.4 The Dynamic and Stochastic General Equilibrium DSCGE Model

Our model is built based on the same assumptions as those of model EXTER, however, it has some specificities to reflect more the structure of the economy of Benin. The most important is the addition of the transfers between the households and the rest of the world, and also between the government and the rest of the world, or the

international assistances. The heart of the model can be described as walrasian. It determines only the relative prices and the other variables of the real sphere of the economy of Benin. The economic agents of the country do not have any control on the world prices like bench on the assumptions of the model EXTER. That is the assumption of the small country price taker. These prices, either from export or import, are entirely given on the world market and constitute an exogenous data in the model. While households maximize their utility subject to their revenue, which depends itself on the endowments in factors of production and on the received transfers, firms maximize their profits subject to the technology and the factors of production available. The government ensures the operation of the public sector and gains its revenue from the taxes, from the customs duties and the various international assistances. In this model, the rest of the world serves more as an external agent of trade. In certain cases, the rest of the world plays also either the role of the Benin citizen abroad who operates transfers of funds, being on the territory, or of international organization which makes transfers to the government. Another specificity of our model is that it is dynamic and stochastic. In addition to estimating in precise way the interrelationships between different factors and markets following a structural change in the economy, it is able to take into account the dynamic effects of simulated policies over many time period. And also, the fact that the model is made stochastic through a technological shock bring us more and more closer to the reality. The equations of the model are grouped in 6 principal blocks that we describe in the next sections.

2.4.1 Production block

The production block is characterized by 6 equations based on two main assumptions. The first is the assumption of substitutability between the factors of production (labor and capital) in Cobb Douglas in the determination of the added value $VA_{j,t}$ in a given sector j at time t and the second is the assumption of perfect complementarity through Leontief between the intermediate demand $DI_{i,t}$ and the added value $VA_{j,t}$. Because of the juxtaposition of the different specifications in the production process, the total production of each branch is determined by a several stages technique of production. Thus for the branches of activities, the production is modeled in two levels. At the first level, $VA_{j,t}$ in branch j is obtained from consumption of the production factors Capital and Labour in each branch with a technology of the type Cobb-Douglas. This is represented in the equation 1.

$$VA_{j,t} = A_j * LD_{j,t}^{\alpha_j} * KD_{j,t}^{1-\alpha_j} \text{ with } j = 1, \dots, 21 \quad (1)$$

$VA_{j,t}$ in value is a Cobb-Douglas function between labour demand $LD_{j,t}$ and

capital demand $KD_{j,t}$. In this equation, $VA_{j,t}$ represent the added value of the sector j at period t ; A_j represent the scale coefficient of Cobb Douglas function of sector j ; $LD_{j,t}$ and $KD_{j,t}$ represent respectively the labour demand and the capital demand of the sector j at period t and α_j represent the elasticity parameter of Cobb-Douglas Function with ($0 < j < 1$).

At the second stage, $VA_{j,t}$ is combined with consumption (inputs) of intermediate demand $DI_{i,t}$ according to a technology of Leontief i.e. with complementary factors in order to produce the composite output $XS_{j,t}$ (for the domestic market and export). This is represented in the equation 2. Here the producer maximize their profit on the basis of concave production function.

$$\begin{aligned} XS_{j,t} &= leontief(VA_{j,t}, DI_{I,t}, v_j, io_j) \\ &= Min\left[\frac{VA_{j,t}}{v_j}, \frac{DI_{i,t}}{io_j}\right] \\ XS_{j,t} &= \frac{VA_{j,t}}{v_j} \text{ with } j = 1, \dots, 21 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where v_j is the share of the added value in the total output, ($0 < v_j < 1$); io_j is the share of the intermediate demand in the total output, ($0 < io_j < 1$) and $v_j + io_j = 1$. The equation of intermediate demand of the branches are determined by functions of the type Leontief, in order to be able to arise the perfect complementarity between the various variables of production.

The intermediate demand ($DI_{i,t}$) for a given product i in the economy is obtained as the sum of the intermediate demand for the good i in the sector j ($DI_{i,j,t}$) in the whole economy.

$$DI_{i,t} = \sum DI_{i,j,t} \quad (3)$$

with

$$DI_{i,j,t} = \alpha_{i,j} * XS_{j,t} \quad (4)$$

In the two last equations 3 and 4, $DI_{i,j,t}$ is the intermediate demand for the good i in the sector j ; $\alpha_{i,j}$ is the quantity of good i used in the production of the good j with ($0 < \alpha_{i,j} < 1$).

The equations of the labour and capital demand are derived from a process of minimization of the production costs subject to the production function of the added value. The equation 5 makes it possible to arise in our model the relation which exists between the demand for labour ($LD_{j,t}$) and the wage. The function of demand for labour have the form:

$$LD_{j,t} = \frac{\alpha_j * PV_{j,t} * VA_{j,t}}{w} \quad (5)$$

$PV_{j,t}$ is the price of the added value of the sector j and w is the average wage rate. The more the wage increase, the more the required quantity of labour decrease. In the same direction, we have :

$$KD_{j,t} = \frac{(1 - \alpha_j) * PV_{j,t} * VA_{j,t}}{r_j} \quad (6)$$

$KD_{j,t}$ is the capital demand of the sector j and r_j is the rate of return to capital in the sector j .

2.4.2 Income and savings of the different agents in the economy

The block of the incomes and the savings concern the 4 economic agents of the economy : household, government, firms and the rest of the world.

In our model, we have only one category of household. The representative household is equipped with a Cobb Douglas preferences and draws its satisfaction from the consumption of goods. Its income comes mainly from the return on the labour supply, the return on the capital paid by the firm, and the transfers coming from the government and exterior or the rest of the world. Generally, the total income of the household is the function :

$$YH_t = w \sum LD_{j,t} + \omega_1 \sum r_j KD_{j,t} + TGH_t + TFH_t + TWH_t \quad (7)$$

TGH_t , TFH_t and TWH_t represent respectively the transfers that the household receive from the government, the firms and the rest of the world and ω_1 is the household share in the total capital. From the total revenue (equation 7), the household pay a proportion of their income as tax that the government collect. That is equation 8.

$$TYH_t = tyh * YH_t \quad (8)$$

TYH_t is the direct taxes on the household income and tyh the tax rate. From the equations 7 and 8, we compute the disposable income as the difference between the total income and the direct taxes on household income.

$$\begin{aligned} DYH_t &= YH_t - TYH_t \\ &= YH_t - (tyh * YH_t) \text{ so that we have} \\ DYH_t &= YH_t * (1 - tyh) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

DYH_t is the disposable income of the household. In the disposable income, the household will save the portion that is not consumed nor transfered. The marginal propensity to save of the household (sh) is obtained from the data of the social

accounting matrix.

$$SH_t = sh * DYH_t \quad (10)$$

SH_t is the savings of household. The remaining part that is the difference between the disposable income and the saving will be consumed by the household.

$$CH_t = YDH_t - SH_t \quad (11)$$

CH_t is the total consumption of the household. This will be seen in more detail in the demand for commodities block.

The firm's income is composed of the transfers from the government, household and the rest of the world. It comprises also the return on the capital paid to the firms as firms in our model are also owner of a part of the total capital.

$$YF_t = \omega_2 \sum r_j K D_{j,t} + TGF_t + THF_t + TWF_t \quad (12)$$

where TGF_t , THF_t and TWF_t represent respectively the transfers from the government, the household and the rest of the world to firms; ω_2 is firms share in total capital. The direct taxes on firms income is a portion of their total income which is perceived by the government. Here also, the tax rate tyf is applied directly to the total income.

$$TYF_t = tyf * YF_t \quad (13)$$

TYF_t is the direct taxes on the firms income. Thus, the disposal income of the firms DYF_t is the difference between their total income (equation 12) and their direct taxes (equation 13).

$$DYF_t = YF_t * (1 - tyf) \quad (14)$$

The saving of the firms SF_t is finally the remaining portion of their disposable income which is not transferred. Their marginal propensity to save sf is obtained from the data of the social accounting matrix.

$$SF_t = sf * DYF_t \quad (15)$$

The following 5 equations gathers the set of the equations of saving and revenues of the government. The rates of indirect tax paid by the branches of activity include the taxes paid on the part of the production sold locally and those paid on the local sales of the imported products. That is, they represent tax perceived on the total domestic consumption. Indirect tax on imported products $ITM_{i,t}$ is computed using the indirect tax rate on importation of goods tm_i , their world price $WPM_{i,t}$, the

nominal exchange rate e and the import demand $M_{i,t}$.

$$ITM_{i,t} = tm_i * e * WPM_{i,t} * M_{i,t} \quad (16)$$

For their part, the revenues from taxation on export are determined using the tax rate on export goods te_i , the domestic export price $PE_{i,t}$ of good i and the quantity of exports $E_{i,t}$. The domestic prices of the goods exported being already in local currency, we do not need anymore the exchange rate in order to convert the revenues from taxation on export. In the majority of the countries, the export taxes are abolished. These taxes are represented as follow:

$$ITE_{i,t} = te_i * PE_{i,t} * E_{i,t} \quad (17)$$

The other indirect taxes on goods are computed using the price of aggregate output of good, the export supply of good, the indirect tax rate on good, and the domestic import price of good. The equation is as follow:

$$OIT_{i,t} = tx_i(P_{i,t} * XS_{i,t} - PE_{i,t} * E_{i,t}) + \frac{tx_i}{1 + tx_i} * PM_{i,t} * M_{i,t} \quad (18)$$

$OIT_{i,t}$ is the other indirect taxes on good i ; $P_{i,t}$ is the price of aggregate output of good i ; tx_i is the indirect tax rate on good i ; $PM_{i,t}$ is the domestic import price of good i .

From the equations 16, 17 and 18 we can now derive the government income YG_t as the summation of other indirect taxes on good, indirect taxes on exportation, indirect taxes on importation, direct taxes on household and firms incomes, return on capital as they own a part of the total capital and transfers from the rest of the world to the government. The equation is as follow:

$$YG_t = (1 - \omega_1 - \omega_2) \sum r_j KD_j, t + \sum ITM_{i,t} + \sum ITE_{i,t} + \sum OIT_{i,t} + TYH_t + TYF_t + TWG_t \quad (19)$$

The government saves the remainder of its revenue after the execution of its public expenditure and its transfers to the households, the firm and the rest of the world. The saving of the government SG_t is a fraction of its revenue. The propensity to save sg is between 0 and 1 and can be obtained from the social accounting matrix.

$$SG_t = sg * YG_t \quad (20)$$

Often, the governments, especially those of developing countries save negatively because they have government expenditure very high and payments of foreign debts

to carry out. It is thus difficult to these governments to lay down objectives of investments.

2.4.3 Prices

The prices play a central role in CGE models. The changes in relative prices generate the reallocation of the factors and the goods in the economy. The prices amongst other things enable us to determine the value of the products, of the commercial flows and even of gross domestic product (GDP). We start with the presentation of the price of the added value $PV_{i,t}$ in the equation 21. It is defined from the value of the total production $P_{i,t} \times XS_{i,t}$, diminished by the total value of the intermediate demand, the whole divided by the volume of the added value. The equation of the price of the added value can be presented in the following way:

$$PV_{i,t} = \frac{P_{i,t}XS_{i,t} - \sum PC_{i,t}DI_{i,j,t}}{VA_{i,t}} \quad (21)$$

$P_{i,t}$ is the price of aggregate output of good i ; $DI_{i,j,t}$ is the intermediate demand for good i in sector j . The following equation 22 enables us to find the domestic prices of the importation. The exchange rate makes it possible to convert the world price of the importation into domestic prices and then we add to it the taxes on the importation and the one of consumption to find the domestic prices of the imported products.

$$PM_{i,t} = PWM_{i,t}(1 + tm_i)(1 + tx_i)e \quad (22)$$

$PM_{i,t}$ is the domestic import price of good i ; $PWM_{i,t}$ is the world price of importation of good i ; tm_i is the tax rate on the import of good i ; tx_i is the indirect tax rate on good i ; e is the nominal exchange rate. The domestic export prices are obtained using the world export price to which is added the effect of the exchange rate and then from which is removed the effect of the export taxes. Given that Benin is a small country price taker, the Beninese producers receive an export price lower than the world price. The world price is initially converted into local currency using the exchange rate, and then the export duties perceived by the government are removed from it. The following equation 23 expresses the relation which exists between the world price $PWE_{i,t}$ and the export domestic price $PE_{i,t}$.

$$PE_{i,t} = \frac{PWE_{i,t} * e}{1 + te_i} \quad (23)$$

te_i is the tax rate on export of good i .

$$PC_{i,t} = \frac{PD_{i,t}DD_{i,t} + PM_{i,t}M_{i,t}}{Q_{i,t}} \quad (24)$$

$PC_{i,t}$ is the price of composite good i , $DD_{i,t}$ is the domestic demand of good i and $Q_{i,t}$ is the demand for composite good i .

Equation 24 describe the price of composite good where we have the price of domestic good $PD_{i,t}$ explained by the following :

$$PD_{i,t} = (1 + tx_i)PL_{i,t} \quad (25)$$

$PL_{i,t}$ is the producer price of domestic good i .

$$P_{i,t} = \frac{PL_{i,t}DS_{i,t} + PE_{i,t}E_{i,t}}{XS_{i,t}} \quad (26)$$

P_i is the price of aggregate output of good i and $E_{i,t}$ is the export supply of good i .

The return on the capital r_j exists for each branch of the economy contrary to the wage which is single and similar with all the branches. This is due to the assumptions of the model which give a mobile character on the labour between the sectors of production whereas the various capital of production is fixed. The return on the capital is calculated using the added value from which one withdraw the value of the labour. The whole is finally divided by the volume of the capital in order to have the return on the capital:

$$r_j = \frac{PV_{j,t}VA_{j,t} - wLD_{j,t}}{KD_{j,t}} \quad (27)$$

$$Pindex_t = \sum \mu_i PV_{i,t} \quad (28)$$

$Pindex_t$ is the price index and μ_i is the share of good i in added value price.

2.4.4 Demand for commodities

The block of the domestic final demand is composed of the demand for household consumption, the demand for investments, the governmental expenditure and the intermediate demands. The following equations describe the different demand functions.

$$CH_t = YDH_t - SH_t \quad (29)$$

CH_t is the total consumption of the household.

$$PC_{i,t}C_{i,t} = PC_{i,t}C_{i,t}^{Min} + \psi_{i,t}^h(CH_t - \sum PC_{i,t}C_{i,t}^{Min}) \quad (30)$$

$PC_{i,t}$ is the Price of Composite Good i ; $C_{i,t}^{Min}$ is the minimum consumption of the household for good i ; $C_{i,t}$ is the quantity of good i demanded by the Household; $\psi_{i,t}^h$ is the share of good i in household consumption.

The incompressible consumption of the household $C_{i,t}^{Min}$ that is the minimum consumption of the household for good i (equation 30) is used to compute the poverty line.

$$z_t = \sum PC_{i,t} C_{i,t}^{Min} \quad (31)$$

where z_t is the period t poverty line.

The firm and the government consumptions are a part of their total revenue. They are defined as follow:

$$CF_{i,t} = \frac{f_{i,t}(1 - sf)}{PC_{i,t}} YDF_t \quad (32)$$

$$CG_{i,t} = \frac{g_{i,t}(1 - sg)}{PC_{i,t}} YDG_t \quad (33)$$

$CF_{i,t}$ and $CG_{i,t}$ are respectively the firm and government consumptions of good i and $f_{i,t}$ and $\psi_{i,t}^G$ are respectively the share of good i in firm and government consumption.

From now, we define total consumption $CT_{i,t}$ in the economy as the summation of the consumption of the household, the firm and the government.

$$CT_{i,t} = CH_{i,t} + CF_{i,t} + CG_{i,t} \quad (34)$$

The demand for investment for a branch in various products is given by:

$$I_{j,t} = \frac{\phi_j I_t}{Pindex_t} \quad (35)$$

where $I_{j,t}$ is the total investment in the sector j at the period t , I_t is the total investment in the economy, ϕ_j is the share of the sector j in the total investment and $Pindex_t$ is the producer price index. The investment price index is more detailed in the price block (equation 28).

The investment demand for good is defined as follow:

$$ID_{i,t} = \sum \nabla_{i,j} I_{j,t} \quad (36)$$

with $ID_{i,t}$, the investment demand for the good i and $\nabla_{i,j}$ the share of investment of the good i in the sector j .

2.4.5 Trade

Beninese producers decide which part of their production to export and which part to sell on the local market. To make this choice, they will refer to several parameters of the local market and the external markets such as the demand, the price and especially the supply and the influence of the competitor producers. There is thus an elasticity of transformation between the products, which makes it possible to determine the part of the production that a branch of activity intends for export or for the local market. The fact that a sector can have several products and to locally sell a product different from that which it exports, confers a finished value on elasticities of transformation. What implies that the increase in the factors of production for one of the products of a branch of activity inevitably does not generate the rise of the production of the other products of the branch. The supply function of goods and services on the two markets of a branch of activity is thus obtained by maximizing its incomes on the two markets subject to a function of transformation with constant elasticity. The equations of production of the exported goods are thus of type CET with elasticity of constant transformation (CET for Constant Elasticity of Transformation).

$$XS_{i,t} = \beta_i * [\gamma_i * E_{i,t}^{R_i} + (1 + \gamma_i) * DS_{i,t}^{R_i}]^{1/R_i} \quad (37)$$

β_i is the scale coefficient of CET Function; $E_{i,t}$ is the export supply of good i ; R_i is the transformation parameter of CET Function; $DS_{i,t}$ is the domestic supply of good i . Consequently, the maximization of the revenues makes it possible to establish an optimal link between the volume supplied on the domestic market and the volume supplied on the foreign market according to a function CET of form:

$$E_{i,t} = DS_{i,t} \left[\left(\frac{PE_{i,t}}{PL_{i,t}} \right) \left(\frac{1 - \gamma_i}{\gamma} \right) \right]^{\eta_i} \quad (38)$$

$PE_{i,t}$ is the Domestic Export Price of Good i ; $PL_{i,t}$ is the producer price of domestic good i ; η_i is the elasticity of transformation.

With the difference of the relations of transformation which exist for the producers sales, the composite product users impose a relation of substitution between the products bought locally and those bought on the rest of the world. The intermediate agents thus choose to be supplied in variable proportions, of local products and imports. The choice between the two sources of procurement is expressed by a function of commercial substitution to elasticity of constant and finished commercial substitution, such as:

$$Q_{i,t} = \lambda_i [\delta_i M_{i,t}^{\rho_i} + (1 - \delta_i) DD_{i,t}^{-\rho_i}]^{1/\rho_i} \quad (39)$$

$Q_{i,t}$ is the Demand for Composite Good i ; λ_i is the scale coefficient of CES Function; δ_i is the distributive Parameter of CES Function; ρ_i is the substitution Parameter; $DD_{i,t}$ is the Domestic Demand of Good i . The imports in commercial products are given by supposing that the intermediate agents will minimize their total expenditure subject to the function CES:

$$M_{i,t} = DD_{i,t} \left[\left(\frac{PD_{i,t}}{PM_{i,t}} \right) \left(\frac{\delta_i}{1 - \delta_i} \right) \right]^{\sigma_i} \quad (40)$$

$PD_{i,t}$ is the Domestic Price of Good i ; $PM_{i,t}$ is the Domestic Import Price of Good i ; σ_i is the Elasticity of Substitution.

The demand of imported product will be done thus using the local and foreign price level. The more the relative price of the market of the local product ($\frac{PD_{i,t}}{PM_{i,t}}$) increases, the more the request of imported products does. Moreover, the domestic consumers choices for the imported products versus the domestic products is represented by the elasticity of substitution. The more this parameter is raised, the more the national consumers strongly react to a change of relative price between the goods produced locally and those imported.

2.4.6 Equilibrium Conditions and Macroeconomic Closure

It is commonly known in the computable general equilibrium models that the closure rules have a great influence on the results of the model determining the way in which the economy will be adjusted following a simulation. It is a matter of determining the variables that will be adjusted to obtain the various levels of equilibrium of the model. In this model, there are 4 principal equations that reflect the equilibrium conditions of the model. The first represents equilibrium on the labour market. In our setting, the labour supply is not fixed between the branches of activity but fixed in the economy itself. The total supply of labour in the economy should then be equal to the overall applications for a job of the various branches of activity to balance this market and it is the wage which is adjusted to ensure this balance.

$$LS_t = \sum LD_{j,t} \quad (41)$$

Apart from the labour, the goods and services market should also balance. The total demand for investment for a given product i and the intermediate demand are set to be equal to the total interior supply of the goods or composite service of the product. The price of market (PC_i), will be adjusted to balance the demand and supply on

each market of goods and services:

$$Q_{i,t} = DI_{i,t} + ID_{i,t} \quad (42)$$

The relation between the saving and the investment constitutes the third equilibrium equation of our model. This equation represents macroeconomic balance between the saving and the investment. According to the assumptions of this closure, the investment is adjusted to take the value of the total savings. As savings, we distinguish the saving from the households, that of the companies, that of the government and that of the rest of the world which is in fact the balance on the current accounts:

$$I = S \quad (43)$$

Finally, the equation of the balance on the current accounts represents the fourth and last equilibrium equation of the model. This equation makes it possible to determine the surplus or deficit of the balance on the current accounts or the level of the rate of real exchange according to the choice of closure which is retained. In our case, since Benin belongs to the zone using franc CFA, the rate of nominal exchange is exogenous and the foreign saving is adjusted to balance this market. We chose this closure via the following equation of the whole of foreign flows which enter the country (foreign imports, capital, transfers), is withdrawn the whole of flows which leave there (exports, transfers...).

$$B = e \sum WPM_i M_{i,t} - e \sum WPE_i E_{i,t} + NLA - TWH(t) + TW F_t + TW G_t + THW_t - TFW_t - TGW_t = 0 \quad (44)$$

2.4.7 Equation of the dynamic of the capital and the technological shock

In order to make our model dynamic and stochastic, we insert an equation of the capital that is inter-temporal and represented as follow:

$$KD_{i,t+1} = (1 - \delta)KD_{i,t} + I_{i,t} \text{ for all } t \in [1, 40]$$

The capital of the next period is the investment of the previous period added to the remaining part of the capital of the previous period according to a depreciation δ of the capital. In addition, the scale coefficient of Cobb Douglas function is considered as the technology and represented as A_j . We assume that A_j exhibit a stochastic

behavior that follows a white noise process.

$$A_j = A_j + \epsilon_j \text{ where } \epsilon_j \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$$

3 Simulations

The simulations are based on the budget published in the GAP that detailed each investment necessary to implement the different policies in the different sectors concerned.

The Government Action Program "Benin Revealed" is a program initiated and designed by President Patrice Talon on the basis of a comprehensive diagnosis of Benin's economic, political and social situation. In view of the diagnosis about Benin economy, the priority axes chosen in the GAP for the reorganization of the framework of macroeconomic policy and maintaining its stability concern:

1. Amelioration of management and monitoring of economic and financial reforms
2. Monitoring the macroeconomic environment
3. Dynamization of the growth and competitiveness and
4. Promotion of the private sector.

This program is a roadmap for government action for the period 2017-2021 for the economic and social transformation of Benin. It is mainly based on three levels namely, consolidating democracy, the rule of law and good governance, initiate the structural transformation of the economy and improve the living conditions of the population. The GAP is subdivided into 45 flagship projects, 95 sectoral projects and 19 institutional reforms. Concerning the flagship projects, these are structuring projects, some of which will be financed by the setting up of public-private partnerships. They are led by agencies placed directly under the supervision of the Presidency of the Republic. It is structured around 9 different sectors that are vital to the people of Benin. It ranges from agriculture and tourism, to upgrading of infrastructure and dynamization of the numeric, electricity, living framework, CIIS, drinking water and finally social protection with the aim of improving living conditions. The following table summarize all the nine sectors with the declination of their respective projects.

Table 1: Talon Government Action Program

Sectors	Projects
Tourism	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Park of the Pendjari 2. Lake City of Ganvié 3. Abomey-Porto Novo Pole 4. Premium Tourism - Tata Somba 5. Historic city of Ouidah 6. Beach resorts
Agriculture	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. High added value sectors (pineapple, Cashew, vegetable products) 8. Conventional sectors (rice, maize, cassava) 9. Continental Aquaculture 10. Bass and middle development Valley of the Ouémé 11. Meat, milk and eggs
Infrastructure	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 12. New Glo-Djigbe Airport 13. Modernization and extension of the Port 14. Redevelopment of the road axis around port 15. Northern Cotonou bypass 16. Fisheries Route (Phase 2) 17. Sèmè Kpodji Porto-Novo Highway 18. Road Djougou - Pehunco - Krou 19. Extension of the road network over 1.362 km
Numeric Sector	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 20. High-Speed Internet 21. Digital terrestrial television 22. Intelligent administration 23. Generalization of e-commerce 24. Generalization of digital Education and training 25. Promotion and development of Digital content
Electricity	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 26. Thermal pathway: ensuring access Competitive to electricity 27. Developing renewable energies 28. Restructuring the national operator and its network 29. Control of energy consumption
Living framework	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 30. Development of the Cotonou Lagoon 31. Development of the lagoon Porto-Novo 32. Waste management in Cotonou 33. Downtown Development (Ganhi) 34. Modernization of the Dantokpa market

Sectors	Projects
	35. Modernization of the Parakou market 36. International Complex Cotonou 37. Business Center in Ghézo 38. Rehabilitation of roads 39. Drainage in Cotonou 40. Social housing program
CIIS	41. City of International Innovation and Knowledge
Drinking Water	42. Responsible exploitation of resources hydraulic 43. Provide access to drinking water for all of the rural and semi-urban population 44. Developing production capacity and distribution in urban and peri-urban areas urban
Social protection	45. Establishment of social protection

Source : PAG (2016)

As we can see on the figure 6, it shows the repartition of the budget over the different sectors for the flagship projects. Tourism, infrastructure and living framework are very important as they represent respectively 9%, 26% and 23% of the whole budget. We can also see on the chart 7 following the evolution of the investments at the level of the flagship projects distributed over the 5 years.

However, our simulations are based on the investments in the sectors of agriculture and agro-industry. This can be justified by the fact that agriculture and agro-industry give higher added value to the GDP of Benin.

The following figure 8 present the values of the shocks. As we are concerned in this paper, to make the shocks in the agricultural and agro-industrial sectors, we computed in percentage the variation of the investments compared with the disposable capital in the sectors. Therefore, the shock can be seen as a percentage change in the investment per period. The dynamic effect have been used by simulating the shock during five years and measure the consequences on the whole economy from the beginning to ten years ahead.

Figure 6: Repartition of the budget

Source : PAG (2016)

Figure 7: Evolution of the investments over 5 years

Source : PAG (2016)

4 Results and Policy Implications

To understand the mechanism, we first use three main variables : the factors of production (Capital and Labor) and also the Added Value. The added value is the factor that contribute the most to the formation of the GDP.

The figure 9 present the share of capital in the different sectors.

We can see that first, the variation in the capital is positive in the agricultural sector and in the agro-industry. This is normal due to the fact that for five years, investments are made directly in those sectors. However, we observe that the effects are more significant in the industrial sector. Agro-industry is linked to agriculture by its demand for the outputs of agricultural products. Agro-industry output depends on the amount of agricultural output, other direct inputs, including labour, fuel, and purchased intermediaries and the stock of private capital in agro-industry. Within these relationships, agriculture affects agro-industry output through its supply of direct inputs, and agriculture affects agro-industry through its investment in agricultural Research and Development, which makes new technologies available to farmers. This can explain the positive and significant evolution of capital in the agro-industry sector. In another hand, the power of CGE model is to show indirect effect of a shock in the other sectors of activity of the economy. Therefore, we can see in the figure that we also have increasing investment in the sectors of transport and telecommunication,

Figure 8: Simulation of the shocks

Source : The authors

financial and enterprise services, electricity, machinery and trade. In the other sectors like education, public administration, accommodation and catering, textile and art, breeding, hunting, fishing and forest, the investment has decreased. To understand why it happen, we should look at the distribution of labour in the figure 10.

By looking at the figure, we can see that in order to finance the agriculture and the agro-industry sectors, the labour is reduced in other sectors; mainly the public administration, education, accomodation, catering, fishing, forest, hunting, breeding etc. Hence people who lose their jobs are constrained to create small business in order to survive. Therefore, in the economy, we observe new investment in private sectors like financial services, transport, enterprise services. However, although the capital in the agricultural sector increase, labor decrease in the first year. This can be explained by the fact that Research and Development allow farmers to use new technologies in they process and less labour force. As consequence, the added value in the agricultural sector decrease in the first year as described in the figure 11.

The results of the simulations are really interesting in the sens that on average, the Growth Domestic Product will increase by 5.9% during the years of implementation of the projects but also, this growth will continue for three years after the GAP as shown in the following figure 12.

Actually, the effects would be higher with investment in high added value and high intermediate demands sectors such as those of Infrastructures or Energy. These latter sectors generate for many a lot more value added by their own production activities but also generate for others a lot of efficiency in the form of high-yield input in the

Figure 9: Impulse responses for the direct and indirect effects : Demand of Capital

Source : The authors

Figure 10: Impulse responses for the direct and indirect effects : Demand of Labor

Source : The authors

Figure 11: Impulse responses for the direct and indirect effects : Added Value

Source : The authors

Figure 12: Evolution of the GDP

Source : The authors

Figure 13: Other factors

Source : The authors

production activities of other sectors of production. While agro-industry, for example, is a sector with a very high added value, Infrastructures or Energy are sectors that boost the productivity and output of dependent sectors such as Agriculture, Transport or Telecommunication.

Apart from those variables, we notice positive and sustainable increase in many other factors. First of all, the figure 13 shows that investment will keep increasing the following years to the simulations. Government revenue, household revenue and enterprise revenue as well as their respective savings will increase significantly during the period of investment and also after the period. This result is really interesting as it shows that the society as a whole and especially households are better off. Their revenue and saving have a sustainable increase.

For growth, two major options are available to East African countries. First, countries base agro-processing development on local consumption as a means to increase the demand for agro-processed commodities. The second option is trade, which allows access to more market opportunities regionally and internationally for locally-produced commodities.

Not only export increases, but also, this generate a lot of taxes revenue to the government (figure 14). African countries have a tremendous potential to expand the merchandise export of agro-industrial products, for which there is growing demand in the international market. Exporting agro-industrial products carries two major benefits: first, such exports can be instrumental in the acquisition of modern technology in return for the mechanization of agriculture; second, sustained growth of agro-industrial exports can help Benin to reduce poverty.

The results reveal that agriculture and agro-industry are indeed an appropriate vehicle for pursuing the goals of growth promotion and income equality. Unlike in

Figure 14: Export taxes

Source : The authors

the past, agriculture is no longer considered as a passive sector, from which resources are squeezed and extracted to support other sectors. Instead, it is believed that agriculture has significant roles in accumulating and self-sustaining growth. It is seen as wielding a major influence on industrialization and economic growth. One possible strategy to enhance the growth not only of the agricultural sectors but even the entire economy is by developing agro-industry, a rural-based industry with business characteristics, which processes agricultural products. Agro-industry has a strategic role to play in development and has wider effects on family welfare and rural community. It can enhance growth and equity improvement at the same time. Agro-industry serves as a bridge for economic transformation, generates employment, supports development in rural areas, prevents urbanization, improves the incomes of the poor, ensures food security, and helps small farmers to survive. Therefore, agro-industry improves income equality while still maintaining economic growth.

Conclusion

This paper aims at evaluating the role of investment in agriculture and agro-industry sectors in Benin. Following an increase in income and urbanization, consumers are more likely to enlarge their food assert including fresh perishable, processed and pre-cooked foods. Farmers also turn to more intensive methods to stand the demand of the blooming market. This process is in accord with greater access to modern inputs such as fertilizers, pesticides, improved seeds and machines. Agro-industry performs a vital position in some of these areas. As such, increase in agricultural investments and production relies upon on enough complementary investments in agro-industry sector.

This fact is often ignored in discussions about the funding desires of agriculture. Our evaluation suggests that it can be useful to leverage investments to increase capital productivity. Our model revealed that investment in agriculture and agro-industry will benefit the country as on average, the GDP will grow by 6% every year in the period of funding and will preserve this trend after 2021. Further, apart from the direct impact on the main sectors, this induces more production in other sectors as economic services, trade and transport and also generate revenues for households, government and enterprises. From this analysis, we recommend that Benin put more emphasis on and direct resources to accelerating agricultural and agro-industry boom. But, growing agricultural spending is insufficient to result in a sustainable growth. Attaining this target requires also non-agricultural investments, such as roads and market development. Constructing rural roads and reducing agricultural transaction costs drastically would encourage growth beyond rural areas.

References

- [1] Adjovi et al; (2006) ” *Impact of the Economic Partnership Agreement on the Economy of Benin: An Analysis Using a Computable General Equilibrium Model*”. MPIA Network session paper.
- [2] Adjovi et al; (2010) ” *Computable general equilibrium models: a tool for ex-ante impact analysis of economic policy measures*”. Capacity Building Project in Design and Analysis of Development Policies.
- [3] Agbodji Ega; (2006) ” *Industrial policy of the free zone in Togo: an approach based on the computable general equilibrium model*”. MPIA Network session paper
- [4] Agbodji et al; (2007) ” *Sectoral Strategy, Poverty and Vulnerability: The Case of Togo*”. 6th PEP Research Network General Meeting.
- [5] Alpanda et al; (2011)
- [6] Alston, J.; (2010) ”The benefits from agricultural research and development, innovation, and productivity growth”. OECD Food, Agriculture and Fisheries Working Papers No.31. Paris, OECD.
- [7] Beryl Onjala; (2016) ” *How can Trade Help Agro-Processing Development in East Africa?*”, Briefing paper, CUTS International.
- [8] Carlos et al; (2016) ” *Agro-industries for development*”, The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- [9] De Maio, Lorenzo, Frances Stewart, and Rolph Van Der Hoeven; (1999) ” *Computable general equilibrium models, adjustment and the poor in Africa*”. World Development 27.3: 453-470.
- [10] EGYPT SSP WORKING PAPER 03; (2016) ” *The Role of Agriculture and the Agro-processing Industry for Development in Egypt*”. IFPRI.
- [11] Luthfi Fatah; (2016) ” *The Potentials of Agro-Industry for Growth Promotion and Equality Improvement in Indonesia*”. Asian Journal of Agriculture and Development, Vol. 3, Nos. 1.
- [12] Jean-Marc Philip; (1992) ” *The use of the CGE for the analysis of the Economic Partnership Agreement between the European Union and the ACP countries: a review of the literature*”. Research documents of the Center of economic Analysis DR 92 -11/12.

-
- [13] Kambou, Gerard, Shantayanan Devarajan, and Mead Over; (1992) ” *The economic impact of AIDS in an African country: simulations with a computable general equilibrium model of Cameroon*”. Journal of African economies 1.1: 109-130.
- [14] Luc Savard and Épiphane Adjovi; (1998) ” *Externalities of health and education and well-being: a model of computable general equilibrium applied in Benin*”. The Economic News 743.
- [15] MFE / DGE; (2004) ” *Impact of the Economic Partnership Agreement with the European Union on the Beninese Economy*”.
- [16] Mougnoil William et al, (2014) ” *Change in trade and household consumption in Cameroon: analysis by a CGEM*”. First Colloquium of the Association of Theoretical and Applied Economics - AETA Cotonou, Benin / November 11-13.
- [17] Narayan, Paresch Kumar; (2004) ” *Economic impact of tourism on Fiji’s economy: empirical evidence from the computable general equilibrium model*”. Tourism Economics 10.4 : 419-433.
- [18] Nicolas Herault, (2004) ” *A Computable General Equilibrium Model (MEGC) to evaluate the effects of openness to international trade: the case of South Africa*”. Center for Development Economics (IFReDE-GRES) Universit Montesquieu Bordeaux IV.
- [19] Nicolas Herault; (2009) ” *The contribution of micro-simulation to general equilibrium models: application to the case of South Africa*”. Economics and Forecasting No. 187.
- [20] Peiris et al; (2007) ”Economic value of climate variability impacts on coconut production in Sri Lanka”
- [21] Sêgnon Aguey; (2014) ” *Commercial liberalization in Togo: impact on the agricultural sector*”.
- [22] Tossou, S. C. (2025). Labor Market Reforms, Flexibility, and Employment Transitions Across Formal and Informal Sectors. arXiv preprint arXiv:2510.03668.
- [23] Thurlow, James, and Dirk Ernst Van Seventer; (2002) ” *A standard computable general equilibrium model for South Africa*”. No. 100. International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI).
- [24] Tossou, S. C. (2025). Essays on Labor Market Reforms and Health Economics (Doctoral dissertation, The University of Wisconsin-Madison).

[25] Adjisse, S. S. (2024). Three Essays on Human Capital Acquisition. The University of Wisconsin-Madison.

[26] Adjisse, S. S. (2022). The legacy of the transatlantic and Indian ocean slave trades on contemporary intent to migrate in Africa.

[27] Tossou, S. C. (2025). Who benefits the most? Direct and indirect effects of a free cesarean section policy in Benin. arXiv preprint arXiv:2510.03658.

List of Figures

1	Benin GDP annual growth rate from 2014 to 2016	4
2	Comparison between Benin and its borderer countries	5
3	Distribution of the capital in 2013	6
4	Distribution of the labor in 2013	6
5	Productivity of the sectors in 2013	8
6	Repartition of the budget	22
7	Evolution of the investments over 5 years	23
8	Simulation of the shocks	24
9	Impulse responses for the direct and indirect effects : Demand of Capital	25
10	Impulse responses for the direct and indirect effects : Demand of Labor	25
11	Impulse responses for the direct and indirect effects : Added Value . .	26
12	Evolution of the GDP	26
13	Other factors	27
14	Export taxes	28